

Publishable Summary for 17RPT01 DOSEtrace

Research capabilities for radiation protection dosimeters

Overview

The overall objective of this project is to improve SI traceable measurements of operational radiation protection quantities in the participating NMIs from emerging countries. For legal measurements according EU COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2013/59/EURATOM traceable measurements are required. This project will ensure that all affected NMIs and DIs have adequate equipment and procedures for the required measuring and assessing human exposure and radioactive contamination of the environment. The main goal of this project is to establish and harmonise the procedures for the calibration of radiation protection dosimeters in various types of radiation protection beams with a special focus on achieving a measurement uncertainty of 5 % ($k=2$) or less. The improvement will be accomplished through research on operational quantities for external radiation exposure and secondary standards for eye lens dosimetry. In addition to these main goals, participating NMIs will prepare individual strategies for radiation protection metrology development and they will discuss them with the EURAMET community in order to ensure a coordinated and optimised approach.

Need

EU COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2013/59/EURATOM (laying down basic safety standards for protection against the dangers arising from exposure to ionising radiation) requires to have adequate equipment and procedures for measuring and assessing exposure of persons and radioactive contamination of environment, assure effectiveness of measures and ensure regular calibration of measuring equipment. Establishing new or improving current calibration services in terms of operational radiation protection quantities will make it easier for technical services to also fulfil the requirements of regulatory authorities for calibrations of radiation monitoring equipment.

For radiation monitoring in cases of external exposure (area or individual monitoring) operational dose equivalent quantities aim to provide a reasonable estimate of the values of the protection under most irradiation conditions. Operational quantities are used for monitoring external exposures because protection quantities are not directly measurable.

The International Commission on Radiation Units and Measurements (ICRU) has defined three operational quantities for external monitoring, in terms of area monitoring: *Ambient dose equivalent* $H^*(d)$ and *Directional dose equivalent* $H'(d)$, and in terms of individual monitoring: *Personal dose equivalent* $H_p(d)$. For the assessment of effective dose a depth $d = 10$ mm is recommended, and for assessing equivalent dose to the skin, and to the hands and feet, a depth $d = 0.07$ mm. For eye-lens dosimetry, a depth of 3 mm is recommended.

Control of patients' exposure to ionizing radiation, as well as of the exposure of personnel working with ionizing radiation in science, medicine or industry has been recognised as the most important need. The obligation of legal metrology and the dissemination of the standards obtained certainly leads to better radiation protection.

Moreover, there are some participating NMIs that do not have an adequate metrological capacity for the calibration of radiation protection equipment at the secondary level. Appropriate training is crucial for the enhancement of research potential at these institutions in order to be able to provide measurement capabilities that fulfil the stakeholders' needs for providing traceable measurements of radiation protection quantities.

Objectives

The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop traceable measurement capabilities for operational radiation protection quantities, including the full characterisation of a measurement setup conversion procedure from air kerma (kinetic energy released per unit mass) to ($H_p(0.07)$, $H_p(3)$, $H_p(10)$, $H'(0.07)$, $H'(3)$, $H^*(10)$)

operational quantities with an uncertainty of 5 % ($k=2$) or less. The applicable photon energy range and dose rate range are 5 keV to 7000 keV and 0.05 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ to 100 Sv/h respectively.

2. To validate the developed measurement capabilities for operational radiation protection quantities, to ensure that within an applicable energy range, from 5 keV to 7 MeV and dose rates, 0.05 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ to 100 Sv/h, the accuracy of the dose measurement under well-defined calibration conditions has to be at least 5 % ($k=2$), by organising and undertaking a intercomparison in dosimetry, including activities related to travelling standards, technical protocols, logistical provisions, and the evaluation of intercomparison results.
3. To develop and submit draft CMCs for the traceable calibration of dosimeters, thus proving the international equivalence of their measurement standards and the calibration and certificates that they issue.
4. For each partner, to develop an individual strategy for the long-term operation of the capacity developed, including possible regulatory support, research collaborations, quality control, the quality management system and accreditation. They should also develop a strategy for offering calibration services from the established facilities to their own country and neighbouring countries. The individual strategies should be discussed within the consortium and with other EURAMET NMIs/DIs, to ensure that a coordinated and optimised approach to the development of traceability in this field is developed for Europe as a whole.

Progress beyond the state of the art and expected results

Objective 1 - To develop traceable measurement capabilities for operational radiation protection quantities, including the full characterisation of a measurement setup conversion procedure from air kerma (kinetic energy released per unit mass) to $H_p(0.07)$, $H_p(3)$, $H_p(10)$, $H'(0.07)$, $H'(3)$, $H^(10)$ operational quantities with an uncertainty of 5 % ($k=2$) or less. The applicable photon energy range and dose rate range are 5 keV to 7000 keV and 0.05 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ to 100 Sv/h respectively.*

The final outcome will be to set up measurement capabilities and a unified code of practice on the procedures for the measurement and secondary realisation of the operational radiation protection quantities, as this will enable harmonisation in the field so that the services provided are comparable across Europe.

Within this project, a methodology for the design of an $H_p(3)$ secondary standard ionization chamber will be developed, with a focus on measurements at the radiology departments. For the $H_p(3)$ secondary standard (ionization chamber) that will be calibrated in one reference beam quality, spectrometric measurements will not be necessary and thus no conversion coefficients from air kerma will be needed. Commercially available ionization chambers can be modified by adding a PMMA (polymethylmethacrylate) phantom around it, to account for the scattering effects, so that the chamber has a relatively constant response in terms of $H_p(3)$. Alternatively, extra scattering material introduced inside the ionization chamber can be used to compensate for the energy dependence of the $H_p(3)$ operational quantity. This will enable the direct calibration of eye lens dosimeters in terms of $H_p(3)$.

Objective 2 - To validate the developed measurement capabilities for operational radiation protection quantities, to ensure that within an applicable energy range, from 5 keV to 7 MeV and dose rates, 0.05 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ to 100 Sv/h, the accuracy of the dose measurement under well-defined calibration conditions has to be at least 5 % ($k=2$), by organising and undertaking a intercomparison in dosimetry, including activities related to travelling standards, technical protocols, logistical provisions, and the evaluation of intercomparison results

An extensive intercomparison exercise will be organised, and laboratories will be able to prove and compare their measurement capabilities for the operational quantities that are most needed by all participants. A target uncertainty of 5 %, or less, and harmonised calibration procedures among participating laboratories will increase confidence in the measurements performed in the calibration laboratories. This will solve the problem of limited accessibility to calibration services in some participating countries.

Objective 3 - To develop and submit draft CMCs for the traceable calibration of dosimeters, thus proving the international equivalence of their measurement standards and the calibration and certificates that they issue

Furthermore, the laboratories will gain more information on three fundamental elements, which will lead to the approval of an institute's CMCs such as: participation in reviewed and approved scientific comparisons, operation of an appropriate and approved quality management system; international peer-review (regional

and inter-regional) of claimed calibration and measurement capabilities. This will lead to the approval of the Institutes' CMCs and they will learn how to submit requests to publish CMCs in the BIPM database.

The knowledge gained will lead to improved measurement capabilities at the calibration laboratories and this will, in turn, enable improvements to be made in radiation safety and in the health protection of workers exposed to ionizing radiation as well as members of the public.

This project will enable users of radiation protection monitoring instruments to meet the requirements of EU COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2013/59/EURATOM (laying down basic safety standards for protection against the dangers arising from exposure to ionizing radiation) by fulfilling the request for adequate equipment and procedures for measuring and assessing personal exposure and radioactive contamination of the environment, whilst assuring the effectiveness of measures, and ensuring the regular calibration of measuring equipment.

Objective 4 - For each partner, to develop an individual strategy for the long-term operation of the capacity developed, including possible regulatory support, research collaborations, the quality control, quality management system and accreditation. They should also develop a strategy for offering calibration services from the established facilities to their own country and neighbouring countries. The individual strategies should be discussed within the consortium and with other EURAMET NMIs/DIs, to ensure that a coordinated and optimised approach to the development of traceability in this field is developed for Europe as a whole

The individual strategies, for the long term operation of the developed capacities, will lead to the provision of calibration services from the established facilities and this will ensure the sustainability of the activities undertaken.

The partners with less developed laboratories will increase their research activities and will establish standards and methods for the calibration of radiation protection dosimeters at an acceptable international level.

Impact

Impact on industrial and other user communities

This project will benefit the industrial community, such as manufacturers of secondary standard ionization chambers for eye lens dosimetry, as well as for the scientific community. It will also improve the accuracy of the measurements made by radiation protection dosimeters at the NMIs/DIs and this will have a direct impact on end users.

Various active and passive personal dosimeters and survey meters are widely used in industry, hospitals, and in the environmental monitoring of radiation, etc. Due to the importance of radiation protection measurements, these instruments need to be calibrated with traceability to national or international standards, but also in beam qualities that are similar to those used in real working conditions (as much as possible).

Impact on the metrology and scientific communities

This project will provide benefit through more accurate dosimetry for occupational exposure in various applications of ionizing radiation, including whole body, extremity and eye lens dose.

Impact will be created for the partners as they will learn, through research, how to design a $H_p(3)$ secondary standard ionization chamber especially for use in the measurement of occupational exposure in medical applications of ionizing radiation.

In particular, an improved secondary standard for eye lens dosimetry will be developed that is more suitable for use in the radiology departments of hospitals. The design of the modified dosimeters will take into account actual use in real practice.

The metrological communities that will benefit from this project will be those that have either not established a traceability chain for radiation protection operational quantities or those that need to improve their traceability chain. Knowledge transfer, from the more experienced NMIs to the less experienced NMIs, on how to establish and validate radiation protection operational quantities will be very beneficial. New or improved calibration and measurement capabilities will be developed and this will lead to familiarisation and drafting of new CMC lines.

Impact on relevant standards

This project will contribute to the implementation of EU COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2013/59/EURATOM by fulfilling the request to have adequate equipment and procedures in place for measuring and assessing human exposure and radioactive contamination of the environment, to assure the effectiveness of measures and to ensure the regular calibration of measuring equipment. Establishing new or improving current calibration services for operational radiation protection quantities will make it easier for technical services to fulfil regulatory requirements for the calibration of radiation monitoring equipment.

Longer-term economic, social and environmental impacts

Social impact will be created by improving the quality of life of the public and of workers. The performance of radiation protection monitoring equipment will be improved by decreasing the measurement uncertainty and by unifying calibration procedures.

At a wider scale, this project will improve collaboration between European NMIs and it will decrease the gap between smaller and the less experienced NMIs and more experienced NMIs.

Project start date and duration:		01 June 2018, 36 months
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Internal Funded Partners: 1 IMBiH, Bosnia and Herzegovina 2 GUM, Poland 3 IRB, Croatia 4 IST, Portugal 5 PTB, Germany 6 SCK•CEN, Belgium 7 SMU, Slovakia 8 TAEK, Turkey 9 VINS, Serbia	External Funded Partners: 10 EEAE, Greece 11 INM, Republic of Moldova 12 NSC-IM, Ukraine 13 USC, Spain	Unfunded Partners: